

PHYSICAL EDUCATION PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CONDUCTING PRACTICAL CLASSES FOR STUDENTS WITH NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: *having familiarized yourself with this application, you will learn about pedagogical technology, its basic principles, new ways of working, the role of the teacher in the process of studying. Increasing your knowledge in pedagogical technology hack, you begin to make him laugh in your work activities.*

Keywords: *practice, physical, pedagogical, technology.*

Over the past years, a wide range of conditions, opportunities have been created in our country, taking into account their interests and aspirations, in order for our youth to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports. A lot of work is being organized, especially in the study of the subject of physical education of our youth with interest, in the implementation of work to strengthen its strong will, equalizing power through competitions in sports, to mature feelings of courage, humanity, love, loyalty to the Native Land. Consequently, such work will help the reader turn youth into a daily way of life, engaged in physical education and sports. One of the main tasks facing physical education teachers is to regularly engage in sports, to teach the necessary information on attentiveness in the process of engaging, to create excellent knowledge of sports in student youth, to spend their free time after school and to teach useful organization.

"In the process of physical education and upbringing of children, it is advisable to teach exercises with the following positive effects, along with providing Didactic Educational Information: - general training exercises;

- special training exercises;
- competitive exercises"

The group of practical exercises includes:

- * walking and running;
- * balance storage;
- * climb and exceed;
- * throwing and hanging items;
- * shipping and handling;

- creeping, crossing all kinds of obstacles"

The advantages of pedagogical technology are many, some of them are the same: modern traditional education. In the XVII century was formed on the basis of the didactic theories of Comenius, which consists of a class-lesson system, which is the most widely used in schools in the world in our time. Modern pedagogical technologies are mainly created in the process of improvement of this system in different directions and are currently developing in different directions. Pedagogical technologies based on the improvement of the pedagogical process, its unification with the personality of the pupil: pedagogy of cooperation, technology of Education based on humanity and kindness. Pedagogical technologies based on activation and acceleration of the activity of the pupil. Problem education, housing, basic signal concepts technologies and kindness. Improvement of Usuv material from didactic materials and developed work-based pedagogical technologies. These technologies are based on such principles as the division of the didactic system of the studied knowledge with optimal content, the systematic review approach to knowledge, the determination of the most effective ways of acquiring knowledge to students. Modern pedagogical technology is one of the factors involved in improving the effectiveness of education, ensuring the implementation of state educational standards, guaranteeing the quality of Education. The use of pedagogical technology in the process of teaching is widespread in our practice. After all, on the basis of democratization and conciliarity of the educational process, the development of democracy and solidarity is in the process. These serve as the driving force behind the implementation of the educational process. Encourages the reader and the teacher to constantly search, to work on a continuous basis. This, in turn, ensures efficiency in education.

Hence, it is necessary to start work from one of their aspects? When we start by beating or emphasizing negative emotions, the question naturally arises as to what we are (a teacher or an expert). The final result of these attempts is to break the texts of different content in relation to the content of education by using specific methods, so that the main division of the emphasis comes from its content, which constitutes the beat, that is, the emphasis on the speaker. Conclusion

lib, didactic thinking means this-constant alokdpari of the content of learning, teaching and learning, search for relationships, aniklash.

In connection with this, Universities, Institutes, educational and educational institutions of a new type-colleges, lyceums, there is an exegesis to acquaint specialists with advanced pedagogical technologies and their theoretical and practical foundations, which is now not enough textbooks, manuals and methodological developments in uzbek language, the reason is the great need to create them. In this regard, the work of uzbek and foreign scientists, who are conducting research on this field, has been achieved by the creation of this use in some attempts to generalize certain literature, use them creatively, and also in some attempts to generalize the work of foreign scientists. In order for students to gain anic knowledge and understanding of pedagogical technologies, it is important to use the opinions of our scientists in the attempts.

In the activities of educators, sometimes useful bulbsada with the concept of "pedagogical technology" are referred to previously disconnected and technologic unproven teaching methods. In essence, pedagogical technology is a new (innovative) approach to teaching, which is characteristic of Uzi. It is characterized by the expression of socio - engineering thought in pedagogy, the image of techno Cratic scientific awareness in the field of pedagogy, a certain standardization of the learning process. In our opinion, as a guide, guyoki kolip, which establishes certain humanitarian norms for the use of various methods of teaching in the course of developing the educational process into pedagogical technology.

USED LITERATURE. USED LITERATURE:

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